

Work commitment and Employee Job Satisfaction: Study of Commercial Banks

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Abstract

The competition in commercial banking sector in Pakistan is at the peak and expectations of every owner of the institution is to be the leader of market, in this context they are eager to find out the determinants of employee job satisfaction, keeping in view the above situation researchers meet together from different disciplines to work out the issue. In this connection study of commercial banks of Sukkur region, Sindh Pakistan was carried out through collecting the primary data from the officers and employees of different commercial banks, used the same through SPSS, and results states that over all model is fit and significant and work commitment is positively and significantly correlated/related to each other.

Key Words: *job satisfaction, work commitment, commercial banks, decision makers, work motivation.*

Introduction

The work commitment was not an increasing concern among the researchers of Management or organizational behavior; recently there is the strong tendency to focus on the broader aspect of work commitment specifically in service sector, which includes specific objects of commitment such as, organization, occupation, union, and one's job (Morrow, 1983; Gordon & Ladd, 1990). Work commitment forms have been shown to predict important work outcomes such as, withdrawal, performance, absenteeism, and tardiness (Wiener & Vardi, 1980; Blau, 1986), and in some cases commitment forms have been reported to be better predictors of work outcomes than other attitudes just like job satisfaction (Mowday, Porter, & Steers, 1982).

Literature Review

The view that WC may be an effective predictor of work outcomes has its roots in the literature. Steers & Rhodes (1978) argued that work outcomes, such as absenteeism, can be understood as a result of conflict among commitments. When employees are committed to factors other than the organization, inside or outside the work environment, they will experience less internal pressure to show up for work. Blau & Boal, Using job Involvement and organizational commitment Interactively to predict Turnover (1989) proposed and examined a conceptual framework utilizing combinations of high and low levels of job involvement and organizational commitment to predict withdrawal and absenteeism. Wiener & Vardi (1980) asserted that because individuals in a work setting simultaneously experience varying degrees of commitment toward several aspects of working life (e.g., the employing organization, the job or task, personal career) work outcomes may be better understood as a function of all such commitment types rather than to one or another separately. They argued that as different objects of WC represent distinct attitudes, different effects on behavioral outcomes can be expected. Given that the object of organizational commitment is the employing organization, the most likely behavior to be affected by this commitment would be organizationally-oriented behavior. Similarly, the most likely behavior to be affected by job commitment would be task-oriented behavior; by occupational commitment, occupation / career- oriented behavior.

Most of the literature regarding WC has traditionally included some or all of the three forms of commitment: organization, job and occupation. One contribution of this study would be the inclusion of an additional form of WC, union commitment (Morrow, 1983), that has received considerable attention in the literature. Gordon, Philpot, Burt, Thompson, & Spiller (1980) argued that the ability of unions to attain their goals is generally based on the loyalty of members and that commitment is part of the very fabric of the union. In several works, union commitment was found to be significantly related to indicators of union effectiveness, such as propensity to strike (Martin, 1986), perceived union effectiveness (Leibowitz, 1983), participation in union activities (Fullagar & Barling, 1989), and union militancy (Black, 1983).

Conceptually, commitment is considered to be a better predictor of withdrawal than job satisfaction, “Commitment as a construct is more global, reflecting a general affective response to the organization as a whole”. Job satisfaction on the other hand, reflects one’s response either to one’s job or to certain aspects of one’s job” (Mowday, Porter, & Steers, 1982)

Job satisfaction focuses on the role of employees in the work place. Thus job satisfaction as affective orientation on the individuals towards the regulations of work roles which they are occupying (Vroom, 1964). According to Armstrong (2006) job satisfaction is a attitude and feeling of people about their work. Positive and favourable attitude towards their job is the indication of job satisfaction and viceversa.

According to Christen, Lyer, & Soberman (2006) they suggested a model of satisfaction comprises of some elements: job related factors, role perceptions, job performance, and firm performance. Layler & Porter (1967) suggested their model of job satisfaction with unlike the previous model which place the importance as the impact of reward system on job satisfaction, according to them extrinsic and intrinsic rewards are not directly linked with the job satisfaction, because of employees perceptions about the deserved pay level. Locke & Lathan (1990), they suggested some different model of job satisfaction. They started from an assumption that the objectives are settled at highest level and high expectations for success in work provide achievements and success in performing the task.

Sampling Design

Sampling for this study comprises of management and officer level employees of different public and private sector commercial banks of sukkur region, sindh, Pakistan.

Data Collection Method

A questionnaire was designed for collection of primary data from above sample: questionnaire comprises of 27 questions related to job satisfaction and work commitment, each response alternative was based on 5 point likert scale. The said questionnaire was administered personally and it was pretested first from the 10 respondents of Habib Bank Limited, Shah Abdul Latif University Branch, before administering it to all the sample.

Statistical Method

In order to check the impact of the variables Reliability analysis was used by checking the cronbach’s alpha, of the data collection instrument through SPSS, Regression and Pearson Correlation analysis was used to check the strength of relationship among variables, either positive or negative, and how much each variable is correlated (highly, average, not related) with otherone.

Results and Discussions

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.818	27

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.674 ^a	.454	.443	.74609954

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Commitment

Model summary is the parameter through which we can conclude over all model fit according to the variables in the equation and error term, and the value of adjusted R-square states that that this model comprises of Employee job satisfaction as dependent variable and work commitment as independent variable is 44.3% fit and 55.7% is the error term which needs to work out, but the contribution of work commitment is debatable and needs much efforts and concentration by the decision makers of commercial banks to meet with the competition.

ANOVA^b

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	24.053	1	24.053	43.210	.000 ^a
	Residual	28.947	52	.557		
	Total	53.000	53			

a. Predictors: (Constant), Work Commitment

b. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

And as we discussed in overall model fit the contribution work commitment towards job satisfaction, ANOVA table states the significance of that contribution and above discussed model of job satisfaction and work commitment is significant at .000 level which again is the good sign.

Coefficients^a

Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.221E-17	.102		.000	1.000
	Work Commitment	.674	.102	.674	6.573	.000

a. Dependent Variable: Job Satisfaction

Results in the coefficients table in the column of standardized coefficients value of beta of work commitment is .674 which is near to one and we concluded that the strength of relationship between work commitment and job satisfaction in commercial banks to powerful, positive and significant.

Correlations

		Job Satisfaction	Work Commitment
Job Satisfaction	Pearson Correlation	1	.674**
	Sig. (1-tailed)		.000
Work Commitment	Pearson Correlation	.674**	1
	Sig. (1-tailed)	.000	

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (1-tailed).

Pearson correlation (1-tailed) is a measure which states the level of correlation of one variable with other variable(s) and these results of job satisfaction and work commitment is positively and highly correlated to each other.

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